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Numerical and Experimental Investigations of Cavitation Phenomena inside the Pilot Stage of the Deflector Jet Servo-Valve

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ABSTRACT Two-stage electrohydraulic servo-valves play an important role in the most modern hydraulic servo control systems for flight wing controls, manufacturing robots, and many engineering applications. The existence of cavitation inside the pilot stage is one of the root causes of self-excited noise, cavitation erosion, system jam, and frequent failures of electrohydraulic servo-valves. Thus, experimental and numerical investigations of the flow field and cavitation phenomena inside the pilot stage of deflector jet servo-valve under different supply pressures conditions are conducted in this paper. An assembly for experimental verification of the flow visualization process that represents the deflector jet pilot stage is produced and discussed. To test and verify the numerical simulations for cavitation phenomena, the flow field characteristics in the deflector jet pilot stage are investigated by using experimental flow visualization. The cavitation inception inside the pilot stage of the deflector jet servo-valve is experimentally confirmed through flow visualization. More importantly, the attached cloud-like cavitation or bubble shedding is observed along with the jet flow and the significant locations of cavitation inception are also identified for varying supply pressures. The profile of turbulent intensity confirms to conclude that turbulent pressure fluctuations contribute to cavitation. The result also shows that the increment of supply pressure intensifies cavitation and output pressure plays a significant role in reducing the intensity of cavitation inside the pilot stage of deflector jet servo-valve. Finally, the numerical results show good agreement with experimental results.

INDEX TERMS Servo-valve, deflector jet servo-valve, turbulent flow, cavitation, numerical simulations.

I. INTRODUCTION

Electro-hydraulic servo-valve is one of the most failure-prone components which has a significant impact on the performance and reliability of the entire servo control systems directly [1]. A detailed review of research that investigates electro-hydraulic servo-valves via computational fluid-dynamic analysis, research studies on novel control systems, and novel configurations based on the use of smart materials for improving performance or reducing cost, were analyzed and discussed by Tamburrano *et al.* [2]. Due to the advantages of high resistance to contamination, fast dynamic response, larger flow control and high reliability, deflector jet servo-valves have been widely applied in many engineering applications. But, the deflector jet servo-valve whose static

and dynamic performance may trouble in achieving precise control of the hydraulic servo control systems by generating flow cavitation. Cavitation is a complex fluid mechanics phenomenon for nozzles, pumps, injectors, turbines, propellers and a variety of other fluid machinery components. It causes undesired effects such as noise, vibration, power loss and erosion of components in hydraulic valves [3]-[6]. The relationship between inlet pressure fluctuations and unsteady cavitation process conditions inside a water hydraulic poppet valve investigated numerically by Liang *et al.* [7]. Their studies revealed that increasing or decreasing the frequency to a certain extent can suppress the enhancement of cavitation and the existence of a groove at valve port can also reduce the intensity of cavitation under

the conditions of inlet pressure fluctuations. Han *et al.* [8] numerically investigated the flow force and cavitation phenomena inside the water hydraulic poppet valves. Their results showed that the innovative structure of valve opening and outlet pressure can help to suppress the enhancement of cavitation inside the valves. Zou *et al.* [9] studied the cavitation in a spool valve with U-grooves and observed that the cavitation inside the valve become more violent with the increase of valve opening and deeper groove depth. Gao *et al.* [10] studied the formation of the vortex and the flow stream inside metering in the spool valve with different valve openings by using finite element and PIV methods. Aiming to highlight the root causes of the self-excited noise inside the pilot stage of the flapper-nozzle servo valve, Chen *et al.* [11] investigated the pressure pulsation characteristics and noise characteristics at three different oil viscosities experimentally. According to their results from both numerical simulations and experimental flow observations, it found that the cavitation shedding phenomenon is intensified with the decreasing of oil viscosity. Moreover, in their studies, the pressure pulsation wave induced by the unsteady cavitation shedding in the flapper-nozzle pilot stage found one of the mechanisms of noise production. However, other researchers analyzed pressure losses and flow characteristics of the spools in directional control valves and servo valves using numerical simulations. Zhang *et al.* [12] analyzed the cavitation erosion, spiral vortex, and energy loss by using pure water flow through the valve port. In the work carried by Sandor *et al.* [13], the higher inlet pressure would produce more intense and more damaging cavitation.

To date, some significant studies on the flow field and cavitation phenomena inside the pilot stage in the hydraulic servo valves were carried out both numerically and experimentally. Jacob *et al.* [14] performed a CFD analysis to study the flow field in the pilot stage of a double nozzle-flapper servo-valve. Their work showed the reliability of the standard turbulence model for the steady-state incompressible fluid flow distribution in the pilot stage of a double nozzle-flapper servo-valve. Li *et al.* [15] conducted experimental and numerical investigations of the cavitation phenomenon inside the pilot stage of the flapper-nozzle servo-valve under variation of Reynolds number ranging from 630 to 2500. In their studies, images of cavitation phenomena in the flow field from the experiment were recorded and compared with CFD simulation results to confirm the locations of cavitation sources. Moreover, the attached cloud-like cavity was examined on the flapper curved surface. Aiming to find out a reasonable flapper shape to reduce the intensity of cavitation, Aung and Li [16] also proposed an innovative rectangular flapper shape. Finally, the effectiveness of the innovative flapper shape was proved by showing the same flow control characteristics as the traditionally used flapper shape. Furthermore, three different flapper shapes were experimentally analyzed by Yang *et al.* [17] to observe cavitation phenomena regarding two different

flapper-nozzle null clearance (0.2 mm and 0.1 mm) under four different flow conditions with the variation of inlet pressures. To provide verification on experimental results and a comprehensive understanding, numerical simulations of the cavitation phenomenon in each flapper shape were also performed. Their results explained that the increment of flapper-nozzle null clearance and inlet pressure intensified the strength of the turbulent jets and cavitation intensity in the flapper-nozzle pilot valve. Finally, the effectiveness of rectangular flapper shape in reducing cavitation in the flapper-nozzle pilot valve was also confirmed. In recent years, focusing on the performance of the pilot stage, some researchers also carried out studies on cavitation phenomena in the electrohydraulic servo-valves. The effectiveness of cavitation reduction deploying microjets around the main-jets in the flapper-nozzle servo-valve was investigated by Yang *et al.* [18]. The mass flow rate measurements and flow visualization process were conducted to validate the numerical results. Their research showed that continuous micro-jets are significantly effective in reducing the cavitation of the flapper-nozzle valve. Moreover, Yang *et al.* [19] investigated cavitation and flow forces under various supply pressures in the flapper-nozzle pilot stage of a hydraulic servo-valve by using continuous mini jets. At the same time, aiming to suppress the intensity of cavitation in the nozzle-flapper servo-valve, the diamond nozzles were also proposed to replace the traditional circular nozzles by Yang *et al.* [20]. In their numerical simulation studies showed that a new structure of the nozzles could reduce the intensity of cavitation without affecting the performance of the servo-valve. On the other hand, Wu *et al.* [21] analyzed the intensity of cavitation phenomena by using LES method and snapshot POD technique in the pilot stage of jet pipe servo-valve. The results showed that increasing the inlet pressure of the jet pipe enhances turbulent components containing smaller vortices, but the flow field becomes more stable by the increment of the deflection angle of the jet pipe. Moreover, aiming to control the quiescent flow when the main stage is at rest, a novel configuration which is composed of two normally closed two-way two-position (2/2) valves actuated by two piezo-electric ring benders for the pilot stage of flapper-nozzle servo-valve was proposed by Tamburrano *et al.* [22].

In order to analyze the design and performance of a deflector jet servo-valve, it is essential to examine the flow field phenomena regarding the physical mechanism inside the pilot stage of a deflector jet servo-valve. Although theoretical modeling for pressure distribution in the pilot stage of deflector jet servo-valve [23]-[27] was studied considering both laminar and turbulent flow states, investigations for the cavitation phenomena inside the deflector jet pilot stage are still limited. Therefore, the study of the flow field and cavitation phenomena in the deflector jet pilot servo-valve is of particular interest to many researchers because of the diversity of their practical

applications in engineering. Thus, experimental and numerical investigations of the flow field and cavitation phenomenon inside the pilot stage of deflection servo-valve are conducted in this paper. In addition, a practical determination method for flow visualization is proposed using an experimental approach. Finally, the numerical simulations results are compared with the experimental results for consistent conditions.

II. WORKING PRINCIPLE OF DEFLECTOR JET PILOT STAGE

The schematic diagram of a typical two-stage deflector jet servo valve is shown in Fig. 1. It is an electrically operated control valve consisting typically of two stages namely a pilot stage and a main stage. According to the structure, the pilot stage employs an electromagnetic torque motor coupled with a hydraulic amplifier that serves as an electromechanical converter and plays a vital role in achieving accurate movement of the main stage (also referred as a spool) for sustaining the overall performance of servo-valve. In the pilot stage of deflector jet servo-valve, the amplifier disk and deflector jet are the core parts that influence both the steady and dynamic performance of the valve significantly. Fig. 1 shows a close-up illustration of the amplifier disk and a deflection flapper. The flapper with a V-shaped guiding groove is precisely placed in between supply nozzle and two receiving ports.

FIGURE 1. Schematic of deflector jet pilot stage in an electro-hydraulic servo-valve.

One end of the deflector jet is connected with the armature and controlled by the output torque proportional to the applied electric current say i of the torque motor. And, another end of the flapper is connected to the spool through feedback spring. When the input electrical signal is received by the coil of the torque motor, the flapper moves in an orthogonal plane to the jet. The flapper groove directs the jet of fluid coming from the fixed supply nozzle to one of the two receiving ports. Thus, the pressure builds up in that port which creates a pressure difference across the main spool and

differential pressure moves the spool in the opposite direction to the movement of the flapper.

The feedback spring (also referred to as a spool positioning feedback spring rod) that connects between the spool and flapper to provide a force balance. As shown in Fig. 1, at the null position that is no current in the torque motor, the fluid coming from supply nozzle through the flapper groove exit is equally distributed in two receiving ports so that the static pressure on the main stage spool ends are equal. The jet flows from the flapper groove exit impinge on the splitting wall of two receiving ports and radial jet flows are formed in the flow domain. A typical flow structure and possible cavitation locations in the pilot stage of the deflector jet servo-valve can be seen in Fig. 2.

FIGURE 2. Closeup views of possible flow pattern at the focal point of the deflector jet pilot stage.

After escaping from the splitting wall, radial jet flow behaves as a free jet and moves symmetrically towards the null clearance. Due to sudden change of velocity and pressure drops beyond the impingement zone in the radial jet flow, the vortex is formed at the edge of the flapper groove tip which may lead to cavitation. Moreover, as the return pressure of the jet flow is nearly the atmospheric pressure, the pressure inside the flow field may become lower than the vapor saturation pressure of hydraulic oil and cavitation will appear at the deflector jet pilot valve. The appearance of cavitation at the null clearance may cause undesired effects such as noise, vibration, power loss and erosion to the valve. Thus, the deflector jet servo-valve, whose static and dynamic performance can be deteriorated by the generated flow cavitation phenomenon, is a vital segment in achieving precise control of electro-hydraulic servo valves. Therefore, the distribution of the flow field and cavitation in the pilot stage has a serious impact on the performance of the valve and even the capability of the entire system which should be investigated to improve the performance of servo-valves.

III. DESCRIPTION OF THE NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

A. COMPUTATIONAL DOMAIN AND MESH MODEL OF DEFLECTOR JET PILOT STAGE

The first step for the analysis of numerical simulations is to build a geometric model of the flow field. Thus, the small part of control volume of flow model inside the pilot stage of deflector jet servo-valve has been generated by using computer-aided design (CAD) software to save the calculation effort, memory and time. Fig. 3 shows the three-dimensional computational domain of the pilot stage in the deflector jet servo-valve.

FIGURE 3. CAD and mesh model of the flow domain (a) Amplifier disk of the deflector jet servo-valve (b) Deflector jet pilot stage flow model (c) Mesh model with derived part.

The key components of computational domain inside the pilot stage of deflector jet servo-valve are the amplifier disk, deflection flapper, amplifier top, and amplifier bottom. The shape of the flow field of the amplifier disk and a detailed three-dimensional structure of the deflector jet pilot stage are shown in Fig. 3(a) and Fig. 3(b) respectively.

The dimensions of the amplifier disk for the study of this paper are shown in Table I. Here, the configuration of two receiving ports A and B as shown in Fig. 3(b) emulates the second stage of the valve, which has not been taking into account the presence of the spool. By importing the

computational domain model into STAR-CCM+ CD-Adapco CFD software, the boundary conditions of the computational flow domain (CFD) model are set as shown in Fig. 3(b). There are three types of boundaries in the computational domains namely: the inlet boundary, the wall boundary and the outlet boundary. Wall type boundaries confining the fluid or solid regions are defined at all other surfaces. For viscous flow, the no-slip stationary condition is applied by default. The inlet pressure of the boundary condition is set at 5 MPa, 7 MPa, and 9 MPa, whereas the outlet pressure varies from 0 to 1 MPa during the calculation both in numerical simulation and experiment in this study. At the same time, the meshing module within STAR CCM+ is used for the computational domain and the surface re-mesh, trimmer, and prime layer mesh models are applied to generate the mesh. A finer mesh is built around the flapper groove region by using a volumetric control block. The prism layer mesh is used with a core volume mesh to generate orthogonal prismatic cells next to wall boundaries.

TABLE I
DETAIL DIMENSIONS OF THE AMPLIFIER DISK OF THE DEFLECTOR JET PILOT STAGE

Symbol	Parameters	Value
D	Distance from the supply nozzle exit to receiving ports	0.86 mm
l_j	Width of null clearance	0.11 mm
l_d	Width of deflection flapper	0.64 mm
S_w	Width of the splitting wall of receiving ports	0.10 mm
w_0	Width of the supply nozzle exit	0.15 mm
w_1	Width of the flapper groove entrance	0.52 mm
w_2	Width of the flapper groove exit	0.14 mm
x_0	Virtual origin	0.33 mm

This layer of the cell is necessary to improve the accuracy of the flow solution. All y^+ wall treatment are selected for $k-\epsilon$ model, which offers the most mesh flexibility with good results on fine meshes ($y^+ < 1$) and intermediate meshes ($1 < y^+ < 30$). To validate the mesh dependency of results, three mesh systems are used for the test. The detailed information of the meshes is shown in Table II.

TABLE II
INFORMATION OF THE MESH SYSTEMS

Mesh model	Largest base size (mm)	Number of prism layers	Number of cells	Skewness value (maximum)
Mesh I	0.00020	5	334250	76 degree
Mesh II	0.00020	7	603477	75 degree
Mesh III	0.00015	7	1012480	73 degree

Fig. 4 shows the calculated simulation results for the pressure along the line l_j of different mesh systems. According to the Fig. 4, the trend of pressure curves using different three mesh systems are similar but the results of mesh I and mesh III are very close. The mesh III with higher number of cells is selected for further simulations.

FIGURE 4. Pressure along the line l_j at null clearance for different mesh systems.

B. GOVERNING EQUATIONS AND SOLVING METHOD

A verity of turbulent models including standard $k-\varepsilon$, Realizable $k-\varepsilon$, and $k-\omega$ models are available in the physics continua of the STAR-CCM+ software. The comparison of mass flow rate, phase 2 (gas) mass flow, and pressure distribution in two receiving ports by using three different turbulent models under 7 MPa supply pressure is shown in Table III.

TABLE III
NUMERICAL RESULTS BY DIFFERENT TURBULENT MODELS

Turbulent model	Mass flow rate (Kg/s)	Phase 2 (gas) mass flow (Kg/s)	Pressure in port A (MPa)	Pressure in port B (MPa)
Standard ($k-\varepsilon$)	0.0075014	3.926e-9	1.211	1.215
Realizable ($k-\varepsilon$)	0.0074980	3.835e-9	1.252	1.257
$k-\omega$	0.0074740	3.783e-9	1.265	1.268

All numerically simulated results given by the standard k-epsilon model, realizable k-epsilon model, and k-omega model have no significant difference. The maximum difference is 0.36% in the comparison of mass flow rates from different turbulent models and it is 3.71% and 4.2% in the comparison of phase 2 (gas) mass flow rate and pressure in two receiving ports A & B respectively. Having a reasonable accuracy for a wide range of turbulent flows and a tolerable difference in results (about 2%) compared to other turbulent models [8, 15], [28]-[29]. Moreover, this is also consistent with previous studies on the cavitating water

hydraulic valves [20], [30]-[32]. Thus, it can be understood that the effect of turbulent model on both qualitative and quantitative results is not significant and therefore, for turbulent characteristics, the set of turbulent kinetic energy and dissipation rate equations are employed by using realizable $k-\varepsilon$ model. The benefit of the Realizable $k-\varepsilon$ model is that it more accurately predicts the spreading involving rotation, boundary layers under strong adverse pressure gradients, separation, and re-circulation [8], [33]-[35].

The continuity equation can be expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0 \quad (1)$$

where ρ , \mathbf{u} , and t are the mixture density, velocity and time respectively. The momentum transfer equation can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial(\rho \mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}) = & -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot [\mu(\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^T)] \\ & + \rho \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{F} + \nabla \cdot \left(\sum_{k=1}^n \alpha_k \rho_k \mathbf{u}_{dr,v} \mathbf{u}_{dr,v} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where p , μ , \mathbf{F} , and \mathbf{g} represent the pressure, the mixture viscosity, the body force and the gravity respectively. The terms n and $\mathbf{u}_{dr,v}$ stand for the phase number and the drift velocity, respectively. The equations for mixture turbulent kinetic energy and its dissipation rate are obtained by the simulation of the mixture as a single phase. Thus, the turbulent kinetic energy k and the dissipation rate ε for the Realizable $k-\varepsilon$ model are given as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial(\rho k)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho k \mathbf{u}) \\ = \nabla \cdot \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k} \right) \nabla k \right] + G_k + G_b - \rho \varepsilon - Y_M + S_k \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial(\rho \varepsilon)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \varepsilon \mathbf{u}) \\ = \nabla \cdot \left[\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \right) \nabla \varepsilon \right] + \rho C_1 S \varepsilon \\ - \rho C_2 \frac{\varepsilon^2}{k + \sqrt{v \varepsilon}} + C_{1\varepsilon} \frac{\varepsilon}{k} C_{2\varepsilon} G_b + S_\varepsilon \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $C_1 = \max[0.43, \frac{\eta}{\eta+5}]$, $\eta = S \frac{k}{\varepsilon}$, $S = \sqrt{2S_{ij}S_{ij}}$. In (3)

and (4), G_k represents the generation of turbulent kinetic energy due to mean velocity gradients, which is calculated as follows: $G_k = \mu_t^2 S^2$. And, G_b is the generation of turbulent kinetic energy due to buoyancy, Y_M represents the contribution of the fluctuating dilatation in-compressible

turbulence to the overall dissipation rate. The terms $\sigma_k = 1.0$ and $\sigma_\varepsilon = 1.2$ are the turbulent Prandtl numbers for k and ε , respectively.

The turbulent viscosity μ_t is calculated as follows:

$$\mu_t = \rho C_\mu \frac{k^2}{\varepsilon} \quad (5)$$

where the model constants are $C_{1\varepsilon} = 1.44$, $C_2 = 1.9$, and $C_\mu = 0.09$. Furthermore, the two-layer model is employed in simulation. This model represents an improved treatment of the near-wall region for turbulent flows at low Reynolds number. The numerical stability problems associated with the non-linear wall-damping functions, necessary in the low Reynolds number $k-\varepsilon$ model to integrate both k and ε equations to the wall, are avoided by sub-dividing the boundary layer into two regions [36]. The demarcation of the two regions is determined by a wall distance based, turbulent Reynolds number, Re_y , defined as

$$Re_y = \frac{\rho y \sqrt{k}}{\mu} \quad (6)$$

where y is the normal distance to the nearest wall. In the fully turbulent region, $Re_y \geq 200$, the standard $k-\varepsilon$ model is applied. In the viscosity affected region $Re_y < 200$, the one equation model is employed. In this layer momentum and k equations are solved same as in realizable $k-\varepsilon$ model.

However, the turbulent viscosity is computed from,

$$\mu_{t,t} = \rho C_\mu l_\mu \sqrt{k} \quad (7)$$

where the length scale, $l_\mu = y C_l^* (1 - \exp(-Re_y / A_\mu))$. The two layer definition, $\mu_{t,t}$ is smoothly blended with high Reynolds number, μ_t definition as

$$\mu_t = F_\mu \mu_{t,t} + (1 - F_\mu) \mu_t \quad (8)$$

where $F_\mu = F_\mu(Re_y)$ is blending function defined such that it is equal to one far from walls and is zero very near to walls.

The ε field is computed from, $\varepsilon = k^{\frac{3}{2}} / l_\varepsilon$. Also, the length scale is $l_\varepsilon = y C_l^* (1 - \exp(-Re_y / A_\varepsilon))$ and where $C_l^* = k C_\mu^{\frac{3}{4}}$, $A_\mu = 70$, $A_\varepsilon = 2 C_l^*$.

C. MODEL OF CAVITATION

Since the existence of non-considerable gases in hydraulic oil is unavoidable in practical conditions, the mixture of liquid and vapor phase has been considered in our study. The mixture is considered as a 'single phase' [37]-[38]. Aiming

to compute the steady-state cavitation phenomena at the interested locations under different inlet pressures, the set of following equations are solved during the flow field simulations.

The mixture density and viscosity are:

$$\rho = \alpha \rho_v + (1 - \alpha) \rho_l \quad (9)$$

$$\mu = \alpha \mu_v + (1 - \alpha) \mu_l \quad (10)$$

Here the subscripts l and v stand for the properties of pure liquid and pure vapor which are assumed to be constant. Where μ_v and μ_l are the vapor and liquid kinetic viscosity respectively. The volume fraction of vapor α can be obtained by:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= \frac{V_v}{V_{cell}} = \frac{N_{bubbles} \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3}{V_v + V_l} \\ &= \frac{n_0 V_l \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3}{n_0 V_l \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3 + V_l} = \frac{n_0 \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3}{1 + n_0 \frac{4}{3} \pi R^3} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where V_{cell} is the volume of the computational cell, V_v and V_l are the volumes occupied by vapor and liquid respectively. The terms $N_{bubbles}$ and n_0 represent the number of bubbles in the computational cell and the number of bubbles per unit volume of liquid. The following cavitation model developed by Schnerr and Sauer cavitation is applied in the numerical simulations [11, 28, 33, 37]. When the cavitation occurs, the mass conservation equation is governed by the vapor transport equations:

$$\frac{\partial(\alpha \rho_v)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha \rho_v \mathbf{u}_v) = R_e - R_c \quad (12)$$

And,

$$R_e = \frac{\rho_v \rho_l}{\rho} \alpha (1 - \alpha) \frac{3}{R_b} \sqrt{\frac{2(p_v - p)}{3\rho_l}} \quad \text{if } p \leq p_v \quad (13)$$

$$R_c = \frac{\rho_v \rho_l}{\rho} \alpha (1 - \alpha) \frac{3}{R_b} \sqrt{\frac{2(p - p_v)}{3\rho_l}} \quad \text{if } p \geq p_v \quad (14)$$

where ρ_v and \mathbf{u}_v are the vapor density and vapor velocity respectively. The terms R_e and R_c are the vapor generation rate and vapor condensation rate respectively. Here, p_v is the saturation pressure of the liquid, and R_b denotes the bobble radius which can be expressed as

$$R_b = \left(\frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \frac{3}{4\pi} \frac{1}{N_{bubbles}} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (15)$$

In solving governing equations, the SIMLEC scheme is used for the pressure-velocity coupling since it allows the higher pressure-correction under relaxation factor that aids to speed up convergence [8, 15, 28], [39]-[40]. The PRESTO! algorithm is adopted for the pressure. In order to maintain both accuracy and convergence stability, a second-order scheme, QUICK, is selected for the volume fraction while the first-order upwind is applied for momentum.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP FOR FLOW VISUALIZATION

To visualize the flow field and cavitation phenomena inside the pilot stage of deflector jet servo-valve, an experimental test rig is developed. Fig. 5 shows the prototype of separated components of test section such as deflector jet test section, flapper, transparent glass holder, black sealing. The transparent glass is made of acrylic (transparent material) so that the flow in the test section can be observed.

1-Deflector jet pilot valve, 2-Flapper feedback spring, 3-Flapper groove, 4-Black sealing, 5-Transparent glass

FIGURE 5. Separated components of deflector jet test section.

Flow visualization is one of the commonly-used methods in fluid dynamics researches. The experimental hydraulic circuit is shown in Fig. 6. Furthermore, a test section that represents the deflector jet pilot stage is produced as shown in Fig. 7. The test section consists of an oil tank, a pump embedded motor, deflection flapper, a flapper holder, a deflector jet valve (test section), connecting pipes and pressure gauges, throttle valves, source of backlight, prism, basement jet assembly, a front and back cover, laptop and a high-speed video camera. The working fluid comes out of the pump station, passes through a throttle valve and enters the amplifier disk. The throttle valves are connected to the supply and return lines to control the pressure on the valve. The related properties of hydraulic oil used in the experiments can be seen in Table IV.

1- Pump-embedded motor, 2 - Filter, 3 - Pressure gauges, 4 - Relief valve, 5 - Throttle valve, 6 - Tested deflector jet assembly, 7 - Light source and holder, 8 - High speed video camera, 9 – Laptop, 10- Tank

FIGURE 6. Hydraulic circuit for experimental flow visualization.

TABLE IV
PROPERTIES OF HYDRAULIC FLUID

Parameter	Density (kg/m ³)	Viscosity (N-s/m ²)	Surface tension (N/m)
Liquid	850	0.0085	0.0273
Vapour	0.025	1×10 ⁻⁵	-

The pressure at upstream of supply port and downstream of return port into the test section are measured by using differential pressure gauges with measuring ranges of 0-16 MPa and 0-4 MPa respectively. The flow visualization can be captured up to 6242 frames-per-second (fps) at full resolutions by using a high-speed video camera (PHANTOM V12.1, Vision research, 100 Dey Road Wayne, New Jersey 07470, USA). It is placed 0.2 m in front of the test section and connected to a laptop so that the recorded images can be displayed immediately in a variety of formats with high-definition 720P. The PHANTOM V12.1-a megapixel camera capable of taking 1 million frames-per-second (fps) at low resolutions. It supports 8 to 12-bits pixel depth and a resolution of up to 1280 × 800 pixels. The lighting source is placed underneath the basement jet assembly to obtain good quality images inside the pilot stage of the deflector jet servo-valve. In every run, a stable flow condition firstly is attained by setting required pressures at the upstream of the supply port. Then, the flow structure and cavitation phenomenon observed in the test section are captured by using the PHANTOM V12.1 high-speed camera and directly transferred to the image processing unit (Laptop). In capturing images, the headlight of the front side is turn-off so that the background light source becomes more effective for visibility. Also, the tests are performed by setting the supply pressures with both top-down and bottom-up variations in the range of 1–12 MPa and consistent observations are selected. The outlet (gauge) pressure ranges from atmospheric

pressure to 1 MPa. The closeup view of flow visualization in the pilot stage of the deflector jet servo-valve is shown in Fig. 7. Furthermore, the detail specification of the experimental apparatus is shown in Table V.

TABLE V
DETAILED SPECIFICATION OF EXPERIMENTAL APPARATUS

Device	Description	Specifications
Servo-valve	Rated supply pressure	21 MPa
	Flow rate	30 L/min
	Maximum possible pressure drop	1 MPa (approximately)
	Maximum delivery rate	2.2 L/min
Pressure gauge	Thread diameter	1.4 cm
	Measuring range	0-16 MPa
	Maximum possible uncertainties in measurements	$\pm 2.5\%$
Camera	Model	PHANTOM V.12.1
	Maximum frames-per-second	1 million (optional)
	Minimum frames-per-second	6242
Light source	Model	Dolan Jenner Fiber-lite X2- R150

1- Laptop, 2 - Phantom high speed camera, 3 - Pressure gauges, 4 - Prism, 5 - Supply port, 6 - Tested deflector jet assembly, 7 - Return port, 8 - Throttle valve, 9 - Back light source, 10- Image view from the test section

FIGURE 7. Photo of experimental assembly with closeup view of flow visualization in the pilot stage of deflector jet pilot valve.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the simulated velocity field under the supply pressure of 7 MPa and outlet pressure of 0 MPa as shown in Fig. 8, it can be seen that the flow comes out from the flapper groove

exit which impinges the splitting wall of the receiving ports with high momentum and flow back to the regions E and F. After nearly reaching at the end of the curved regions E and F, moves towards in the region of C and D. The gap between the supply nozzle to receiving ports is 0.86 ± 0.005 mm. When the flapper is installed in the middle of the gap then the length of the null clearance becomes 0.11 mm. At the middle position of the flapper, the computational results of pressure distribution and vapor fraction contour image can also be seen at the zoom view in Fig. 8. Fig. 8 reveals that the low-pressure zone is formed at the flapper groove exit tip due to the radial flow and sharp edge of the flapper groove nozzle tip. As we know, cavitation phenomena will appear in the liquid medium where the local pressure is lower than the saturated vapor pressure at ambient temperature. Consequently, the occurrence of the attached cloud-like cavitation initiation at the flapper groove exit tip can be seen in Fig. 8 (at the zoom view of vapor fraction).

FIGURE 8. Numerical simulations under the supply pressure of 7MPa.

At the same time, numerical simulation results of the computational domain confirm the locations of the cavitation source in the null clearance of the deflector jet pilot stage. As shown in Fig. 9, both numerical and experimental data depicts that the mass flow rate at the outlet of the deflector jet pilot stage increases gradually in terms of increasing supply pressures. This indicates that computed numerical

simulations for mass flow rates exhibit a good agreement with experimental data.

FIGURE 9. Numerical results and experimental data of mass flow rate at the outlet in the deflector jet pilot stage under different supply pressures.

However, the static pressure in receiving ports for varying supply pressure of 5 to 9 MPa whereas the outlet pressure is kept at 0 MPa are depicted in Fig. 10. Experimental data of pressure distribution in receiving ports A & B at different supply pressure conditions are also shown in Fig. 10. In both experimental data and numerical simulation results, the pressure in receiving ports A & B increases with the increment of supply pressures from 5 to 9 MPa. The position of the flapper is kept in the middle. Fig. 10 also reveals that the experimental data is in very good agreement with numerical simulations.

FIGURE 10. Numerical and experimental results of pressure distributions in two receiving ports A & B under varying supply pressures.

Moreover, the calculated numerical results of static pressure distribution along the line probe (at the points of (-0.00135 mm, 0 mm, -0.00035 mm) and (0.00135 mm, 0 mm, -0.00035 mm)) at the location of null clearance under varying supply pressure from 5 to 9 MPa are shown in Fig.

11. The pressure distribution at the null clearance of the deflector jet pilot valve is nearly symmetric around the y-axis.

FIGURE 11. Pressure distribution without outlet pressure at the line probe just before the flapper groove exit in the null clearance of the deflector jet pilot stage.

As shown in Fig. 11, the low pressure is significantly increasing at the narrow flow path of the null clearance with the increment of supply pressures. The low-pressure zone and re-circulation zone at the null clearance in the deflector jet pilot stage are not only created by turbulent pressure fluctuations but also high velocities at the sharp edges of the flapper groove exit tip. Furthermore, to obtain comparable information with experimental results, the vapor fraction contour distributions of the calculated numerical simulations are taken at the middle (at the plane $z = 0$ mm) and amplifier top plane (at the plane of $z = 0.95$ mm) of the three-dimensional computational domain as shown in Fig. 12. Fig. 12 depicts that the occurrence of cavitation initiation at the flapper groove exit tips under the supply pressure of 5 MPa. At this supply pressure, cavitation phenomena can be observed slightly in experimental images. Most importantly, both numerical simulation and experimental flow visualization result in Fig. 12 show that the increment of supply pressure from 5 to 9 MPa intensifies cavitation phenomena at the null clearance inside the pilot stage of deflector jet servo-valve. The numerically simulated results provide additional comprehensive information. Moreover, the locations like the null clearance (especially between the flapper groove exit to housing wall of receiving ports), deflector jet groove nozzle tip, flapper surface, regions E, and F are significant locations of cavitation in the deflector jet pilot stage. The attached cavity at the location between flapper groove to receiving ports housing wall can be found in both experimental recorded image and vapor fraction of numerical simulations. Furthermore, the vapor fraction contour of the numerical results exhibits a good agreement with the experimental image at the plane of $z=0.95$ mm. The results also reveal that the attached cavity shedding leading to the other sides of flapper groove exit becomes longer and longer with the increase of the supply pressures.

FIGURE 12. Experimental observations and numerical simulations of cavitating jets in the pilot stage under different supply pressures. (In numerical simulations, red/light-gray: gas only, blue/dark-gray: liquid only. bright areas show fluctuation between the liquid and gas phases. In experimental results, black/dark-black: cavity or gas bubbles, yellow: hydraulic oil)

Due to the effect of the narrow path in increasing the low-pressure area, the intensity of cavitation inside under the supply pressure of 9 MPa at the null clearance is more notable than the other supply pressures. It is clear from the physical mechanism of flow distribution around the narrow gap of the flapper groove exit and housing wall of receiving ports that the turbulent pressure fluctuations, as well as high velocities at the sharp edges of flapper groove exit, are the root cause of occurrence of cavitation in the deflector jet pilot stage. However, the numerical results of vapor fraction of phase 2 (gas) without outlet pressure (at 0 MPa) and with outlet pressure (at 1 MPa) along with the line probe at the null clearance inside the pilot stage under different supply pressures from 5 to 9 MPa also depicted in Fig. 13. Here, the volume fraction 0 represents hydraulic liquid/oil and 1 stands for vapor or liquid/oil gas. When the outlet pressure is kept at 0 MPa, the vapor fraction of phase 2 (gas) changes very rapidly under varying supply pressures from 5 to 9 MPa at the position of flapper groove exit tip area that is from -0.007 to 0.007 mm. The trends of curves of vapor fraction of phase 2 (gas) along the line probe at the null clearance in the deflector jet pilot stage are almost identical. As shown in Fig. 13, the volume fraction of phase 2 (gas) along the line probe at the null clearance inside the pilot stage under different supply pressures changes notably when the outlet pressure increases from 0 to 1 MPa. And, thus the pressure

differences across the narrow path of null clearance are highly changed.

FIGURE 13. Volume fraction of phase 2 (gas) distribution without (at 0 MPa) and with outlet pressure (at 1 MPa) at the line probe just before the flapper groove exit in the null clearance of the deflector jet pilot stage under varying supply pressures from 5 to 9 MPa.

However, the increment of output pressure like 1 MPa can dramatically suppress the fluctuation of volume fraction of phase 2 (gas) along with the line probe at the null clearance inside the deflector jet pilot stage under different supply pressure from 5 to 9 MPa. Therefore, the velocity distribution inside the deflector jet pilot stage, the pressure distribution on the null clearance and the vapor volume fraction through the null clearance have a significant influence on the cavitation.

FIGURE 14. Pressure distribution with outlet pressure of 1 MPa at the line probe just before the flapper groove exit in the null clearance of the deflector jet pilot stage.

Most importantly, the output pressure plays significant roles to suppress the intensity of cavitation formation inside the pilot stage. Furthermore, the distributions of static pressure along the line probe of the null clearance are obtained from the numerical simulations under the outlet pressure and

different supply pressures can be seen in Fig. 14. The outlet pressure is kept at 1 MPa, whereas the supply pressure varies from 5 to 9 MPa. Fig. 14 reveals that the distributions of static pressure along with the line probe of the null clearance in the deflector jet pilot stage change notably when the outlet pressure is kept at 1 MPa. There are notable changes inside the pilot stage of the deflector jet servo-valve because the outlet pressure has a significant influence on the pressure distribution. And thus the low-pressure zone is reduced. As the pressure distribution has a great relationship with the cavitation phenomena, the intensity of the cavitation can be reduced by the increment of the outlet pressure at a certain value. To quantitatively compare the numerical simulations and experimental data, Fig. 15 depicts the mass flow rates with and without outlet pressure at the outlet inside the deflector jet pilot stage under various supply pressure of 5 MPa to 9 MPa.

FIGURE 15. Numerical results and experimental data of mass flow rate at the outlet with and without outlet pressure in the deflector jet pilot stage under different supply pressures.

As one of the important flow characteristics, null leakage is denoted by the mass flow rate at the outlet. The mass flow rate with outlet pressure at the outlet of the pilot stage decreases while the outlet pressure is kept at 1 MPa. Moreover, the maximum difference is 1.98% in the comparison of mass flow rates with outlet pressure of 1 MPa at the outlet in the pilot stage under 7 MPa supply pressure both numerically and experimentally. As shown in Figs. 13 and 15, the mass flow rate and the vapor mass flow rate change notably when the outlet pressure varies from 0 MPa to 1 MPa. This indicates that numerical mass flow rates with outlet pressure of 1 MPa at the outlet of the deflector jet pilot stage exhibit a good agreement with experimental results. Most importantly, both numerical simulations and experimental flow visualization under the supply pressure of 9 MPa in Fig. 16 show that the increment of outlet pressure from 0 to 1 MPa suppresses cavitation phenomena at the null clearance inside the pilot stage of deflector jet servo-valve.

FIGURE 16. Experimental observations and numerical simulations of cavitating jets in the pilot stage under the supply pressure of 9 MPa and two different outlet pressures. (In numerical simulations, red/light-gray: gas only, blue/dark-gray: liquid only. bright areas show fluctuation between the liquid and gas phases. In experimental results, black/dark-black: cavity or gas bubbles, yellow: hydraulic oil)

Furthermore, the effect of outlet pressure on the vapor fraction contour of the numerical results exhibits a good agreement with the experimental image at the plane of $z=0.95$ mm. The results also reveal that the gas bubbles are disappeared and attached cavity shedding at the null clearance inside the pilot stage of the deflector jet servo-valve significantly suppressed with the increase of the outlet pressures at 1 MPa. From this comparison, it can be understood that the influence of outlet pressure on both qualitative and quantitative results is significant in reducing the low-pressure zone and cavitation intensity as well.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Due to the importance and widespread usage of deflector jet servo-valve in many engineering applications, this paper investigates the cavitation phenomena inside the deflector jet pilot stage both numerically and experimentally. The test rig in terms of design and setup is the core module of the experimental platform. An assembly that represents the deflector jet pilot stage is produced and discussed in this study. Finally, from numerical and experimental results the following conclusions are made.

1. When the position of the flapper is in the middle, the mass flow rate at the outlet and the pressure in receiving ports A & B increases with the increment of supply pressures. Both experimental data and numerical simulations results for mass flow rate at the outlet and pressure distribution in receiving ports A & B are in good agreement.
2. The numerically computed cavitation inception inside the pilot stage of the deflector jet servo-valve is experimentally confirmed through flow visualization. The intensity of

cavitation inside the pilot stage is weak when the supply pressure is lower. However, the intensity of cavitation becomes much stronger with the increase in supply pressure. Most importantly, the higher supply pressure makes the flow start to separate from the flapper groove exit tip and noticeably attached cavity starts to be observed.

3. The location of cavitation in the pilot stage of deflector jet servo-valve is identified and experimental flow visualization is compared with the numerical simulations. The deflector jet groove exit tip, flapper surface, and the flapper groove exit to the housing wall of receiving ports are significant locations of attached cloud-like cavitation in the deflector jet pilot stage. The profile of velocity, pressure and vapor volume fraction distributions at the small vicinity of null clearance inside the deflector jet pilot stage confirm to conclude that turbulent pressure fluctuations and high velocities at the sharp edges of the flapper groove exit tip contribute to cavitation.

4. However, it is also possible to conclude that the increment of output pressure has no significant effect on the trend of mass flow rate at the outlet of the deflector jet pilot stage but the effect of cavitation reduction is notable. Based on analyzing the numerical simulation and experimental results with and without outlet pressure, it can be found that the gas bubbles are disappeared and attached cavity shedding at the null clearance inside the pilot stage of the deflector jet servo-valve with the increase of the outlet pressure is significantly suppressed.

5. Although due to very complex flow field, imperfectness invisibility, micro-scale measurement, imperfect shaping, and installation are unavoidable in current experimental results, the cavitation model for the flow field of the pilot stage and numerical implementation presented in this paper are reliable and helpful for the future design to improve the performance of the deflector jet servo-valve.

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